

EKOLOGIYA” VA “TIL” TUSHUNCHALARINING O‘ZARO MUNOSABATI FAN SOHALARI INTEGRATSIYASINING NAZARIY ASOSI SIFATIDA

Abduvaxabova Dilnoza Nurmaxamatovna
Filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent
Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent
Axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
abduvaxabova0504@mail.ru

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17932127>

Annotatsiya Maqolada «ekologiya» va «tilshunoslik» tushunchalarining o'zaro bog'liqligi hamda fanlararo integratsiya jarayonida ularning ahamiyati yoritilgan. Insoniyatning tabiat bilan munosabatlari, ekologik muammolarning ijtimoiy oqibatlari, ekologik media va ilmiy diskursning aholi ongini shakllantirishdagi roli tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, tilning atrof-muhit bilan o'zaro ta'siri, tillarning yo'qolishi va ularni asrab qolish masalalari, shuningdek, biomadaniy xilmaxillikni saqlashda xalqaro tashkilotlarning faoliyatiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ekologiya, til, til ekologiyasi, ekolingvistika, ekologik diskurs, til yo'qolishi.

Abstract. *The article highlights the interrelation between the concepts of "ecology" and "linguistics," as well as their significance in the process of interdisciplinary integration. It analyzes humanity's relationship with nature, the social consequences of environmental problems, and the role of environmental media and scientific discourse in shaping public consciousness. Particular attention is given to the interaction between language and the environment, the issues of language extinction and preservation, as well as the activities of international organizations in maintaining biocultural diversity.*

Keywords: *ecology, language, language ecology, ecolinguistics, environmental discourse, language extinction.*

For centuries, humans have maintained a close relationship with nature, dependent largely on weather conditions and seeking the safest places to live, gradually shifting from codependent relationships to predatory and consumerist ones. Through natural evolution and technological development, humans have conquered nature, bending it to their own laws and taking for free what they needed for survival. However, in the last few decades, the environmental situation has worsened. This deterioration has led to a number of social consequences: the active publication of relevant articles in the scientific community and the engagement of the media and the public with environmental issues; the spread of social movements in support of nature, such as Greenpeace; and the emergence of a value-based potential in environmental media discourse aimed at fostering environmental awareness. Media and scientific environmental discourse equally contribute to the formation of value attitudes and behavior patterns among the population. Thus, the first type of discourse—media environmental discourse—has a more expressive arsenal of

linguistic means and is guided not only by scientific facts but also frequently utilizes public opinion through the publication of social surveys to influence and persuade audiences. The development of the second type of discourse—scientific environmental discourse—is a response to public concern about the unstable interaction between nature and humans. The combination of these factors has led to the transformation of the term "ecology," which has received a new interpretation and expanded its meaning, as well as to the use of derivatives such as "ecological" and "ecological" in oral and written speech.

With the integration of various fields of knowledge and experiments at the intersection of sciences [Гончарова, 2020. с.27], a new branch of linguistics, called ecolinguistics, has developed. This field of study originated abroad and was initially described in English. Due to the fact that several scholars worked in this field concurrently, and the topic subsequently attracted the interest of Russian linguists, many questions arose regarding the name "ecolinguistics," the terminology used in this field, and the goals, methods, and objectives of ecolinguistics.

It is traditionally believed that the concepts of ecology and language were first linked by E. Haugen in 1970 in his report "The Ecology of Language" [Haugen, 2018. p.90]. The main proposition of this report was that languages are interdependent. According to the American linguist, languages compete, and the survival of languages depends on the use of languages by groups of people and the existence of languages in the consciousness of these groups. E. Haugen also defined the subject of language ecology as "the study of the relationship between languages in the human mind and in a multilingual society," as well as "the study of the interaction between a particular language and its environment" [Haugen, 2018. p.90]. By "The true environment of a language," the scholar understands the actual linguistic environment and explains that the true linguistic environment is a society that uses language as one of its codes. Language exists only in the minds of its users and functions only when it connects users with each other and with nature, i.e., with the social or natural environment of language users .

E. Haugen notes the unimportance of the field's name, but believes that the term "ecology of language" is most appropriate as a name for the emerging field of linguistics, as it reflects the full depth of the questions that arise within ecolinguistics. The researcher sees the main goal of ecology of language as collaboration between linguistics and other humanities to identify patterns of interaction between society and language, or between language and its environment. As an example, E. Haugen cites the enrichment of minority languages, so that the latter become "richer" and can serve for the benefit of humanity. A. Fill notes [Fill, 2018. p.188] that Haugen's

approach to language ecology subsequently developed around the study of endangered languages. Haugen's followers were interested in the causes of language extinction and methods for saving them, which was later pursued by organizations such as TERRALINGUA [<https://terralingua.org/>]. This community, through its periodical journal, publishes stories about endangered languages and their relationship with the culture and traditions of small peoples.

The TERRALINGUA community has existed since 1996 and aims to raise international awareness of biocultural diversity. The community calls for the protection of all the world's languages, cultures, and all living beings with whom we share this earth, raises the issue of combating deforestation, and examines the languages of small peoples and their contribution to human development. This fact demonstrates the TERRALINGUA community's commitment to the field of language ecology as it is understood internationally.

Some researchers believe that Michael Kirkwood Halliday should be considered the founder of ecolinguistics. In his report "New Ways of Meaning: The Challenge to Applied Linguistics," he outlined a range of issues to be researched [Halliday, 2018. p.288]. This range of issues includes the role of language in shaping environmental awareness, specifically the influence of language on the process of adopting socially dictated value systems. Furthermore, these value systems shape behavioral patterns, linking linguistic processes to the modeling of human behavior in relation to the environment. Furthermore, M.K. Halliday emphasized the importance of studying the availability of linguistic means for conveying information about the state of the environment and human interaction with nature.

According to N.N. Kislitsina, ecolinguistics is "one of the modern scientific directions in the field of linguistics, which was formed at the intersection of social (the relationship between social and linguistic structures at different stages of the development of ethnogenesis), psychological (problems of speech influence) and philosophical (manifestation in language of general properties and patterns of development of society and cognition) directions in linguistics" [Кислицына, 2003. с. 42]. Because ecolinguistics is considered a young science, its terminology is still evolving. During its infancy, two terms initially emerged to describe this field: "ecology of language" (E. Haugen) and "ecological linguistics/ecolinguistics" (M.K. Halliday).

Conclusion. The analysis shows that the concepts of ecology and language have expanded beyond their traditional boundaries and gradually merged into an interdisciplinary field. This field addresses the interdependence of languages, their preservation, and their role in shaping environmental awareness. It also highlights the

impact of discourse on social values and behavior, while emphasizing the importance of maintaining biocultural diversity. Overall, ecolinguistics is developing as a modern branch of linguistics that responds to global environmental and social challenges.

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